

**Spectroscopic studies and DFT studies to unveal the structural and vibrational insights of
(2E,4E,6E,8E)-3,7-dimethyl-9-(2,6,6-trimethylcyclohexen-1-yl)nona-2,4,6,8-tetraen-1-ol**

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Abstract

In this study, precise vibrational characteristics and assignments of (2E,4E,6E,8E)-3,7-dimethyl-9-(2,6,6-trimethylcyclohex-1-en-1-yl)nona-2,4,6,8-tetraen-1-ol, pharmaceutically well-known as Retinol (hereafter abbreviated as **RT**), were reported utilizing combined spectroscopy observations and theoretical density functional theory computations. The analysis of normal coordinates was used to identify the characteristic frequencies of functional groups and assign bands, and the experimental and simulated spectra (IR and Raman) were compared. To reproduce the geometrical parameters, harmonic frequencies, and electronic transitions, density functional theory (DFT) simulations were performed at the B3LYP and WB97XD level of functional with the approximation 6-311++G(d,p). To comprehend the chemical stability and intramolecular charge transfer features of **RT**, molecular orbital calculations such as natural bond orbitals (NBOs) and HOMO-LUMO energy gap were carried out at the WB97XD level of DFT. Moreover, the reduced density gradient and isosurface density plots were used to find the strength of non-covalent interactions within the molecules. The condensed Fukui functions were predicted and molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) surface maps were generated to identify electrophilic/nucleophilic regions. Quantum topological atoms in molecule (QTAIM) analysis was performed to investigate the nature and strength of hydrogen bonding interactions. The biological activity of RT was studied by molecular docking analysis. The active binding target residues and binding energy of **RT** against plasma **RT** binding protein and Retinoid-X receptors (alpha, beta and gamma) were analyzed.

Keywords: Density functional theory, Vibrational spectra, NBO analysis, Non-covalent interactions

1. Introduction

(2E,4E,6E,8E)-3,7-dimethyl-9-(2,6,6-trimethylcyclohex-1-en-1-yl)nona-2,4,6,8-tetraen-1-ol (**RT**) is known for its application as dietary supplement. It is found in certain applications include cellular development, anti-skin aging, etc. The replacing the hydroxyl group in RT with carboxylic acid yields retinoic acid. Retinoic acid interacts with a family of nuclear receptors known as the retinoic acid receptors (RARs) to carry out its physiological actions [1, 2]. Retinoids are a huge family of both natural and biologically active forms of vitamin A. It is widely used to treat many types of human cancers and dermatological diseases [3,4]. Additionally, it has been demonstrated to inhibit the growth and development of numerous tumor types in people, including skin, gastrointestinal, breast, oral cavity, prostatic, lung, hepatic, and bladder malignancies [5-7].

To understand the structure-activity relationship of **RT**, the analysis of the molecules at an atomic level is essential. In recent years, some noticeable efforts have been made to investigate the structural aspects of retinoids. Jonathan Urbach reported the conformational analysis and the structure-activity relationship of all-trans, 9-cis, 6-cis, and 13-cis retinoic acid and investigated the vibrational spectra as well [8]. Molecular structure and vibrational spectroscopic characteristics of β -carotene were carried out by S. Schlucker *et al.* [9] using density functional theory (DFT) functional with BPW91/6-31G* basis set. Chihara and Waddell have reported the tentative assignment of all-trans-retinol in addition to all-trans-retinal and all-trans-retinoic acid [10]. The molecular docking and the parameters of quantum chemical calculations of (2E,4E,6E,8E)-9-(4-Methoxy-2,3,6-Trimethylphenyl)-3,7-Dimethylnonane-2,4,6,8-Tetraenoic acid were investigated by Chakkaravarthy *et al.* [11]. Francesco Luigi Gervasio *et al.* [12] have reported the Low-frequency infrared and Raman spectra of all-trans-retinal. DNA interaction with retinol and retinoic acid was investigated by Mandeville *et al.* [13]. Larry senak and co-workers have investigated the vibrational spectroscopy of Retinol-Binding Protein (CRBP-I) and Retinal [14]. Karthick *et al.* have studied the molecular interactions and vibrational aspects of Tretinoin extensively [15]. LemiTürker *et al.* [16] investigated the molecular electrostatic potential and HOMO LUMO has been proposed through MM2 investigations.

It is found from the literature that the detailed structural properties and quantum chemical parameters of **RT** with dispersion-corrected modern functionals were not yet reported. It is obvious from the literature that quantum chemical calculations are fairly very popular because of their effectiveness in predicting the properties of molecules and vibrational spectra of medium-to-large

size molecules [17–19]. In the present work, the experimental IR and Raman spectra of RT were compared with simulated vibrational spectra to reveal the coupled modes of vibrations. The quantum descriptors of RT include electron density distribution in highest occupied molecular orbital (HUMO), lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) and reactive descriptors were computed using WB97XD/6-311++G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) approximation levels using Gaussian 09 software [20]. To deduce the charge delocalization within the RT molecule, the natural bond orbital (NBO) analysis was performed using the same level of basis functionals. For a better understanding of electrophilic/nucleophilic sites of RT, the isosurface map was generated based on electrostatic potential of atoms. Moreover, the molecular docking studies were performed to recognize target binding sites of retinol against retinoid-X receptors.

2. Experimental details

A white crystalline form of RT with a reported purity of about 99% was procured from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Ltd. (India). The FT-IR spectrum of RT was recorded in the wavenumber region 4000 – 500 cm^{-1} at room temperature using the Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer in which a KBr beam splitter was used. The FT-Raman spectrum of RT was recorded in the wavenumber region 3500-100 cm^{-1} using Bruker RFS 27 using Nd: YAG laser as an excitation wavelength with the spectral resolution of $\pm 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

3. Computational details

The use of computational analysis often provides support in favor of experimental findings. In this work, DFT calculations were performed on the electronic structure of RT using the Gaussian 09 program package at WB97XD/6-311++G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) methods to its obtain optimum energy structure (minimum energy), stabilization energies, vibrational normal modes and UV-Vis absorption wavelengths. The Gauss view 5.0 interface program was used for isodensity surface plots and for the visualizing Cartesian coordinate displacements of vibrational modes [21]. The vibration modes corresponding to the IR and Raman peaks were identified with the aid of PED obtained from MOLVIB program version 7.0 [22]. Natural bond orbital (NBO) analysis [23] was carried out using the NBO 3.1 interface program of Gaussian 09 package at DFT method with WB97XD/6-311++G(d,p) basis set to find the charge transfer interactions such as LP \rightarrow BD* and BD \rightarrow BD* (LP- lone pair orbitals, BD – bonding orbitals, BD* - antibonding orbitals). Moreover, the intramolecular interactions were identified by using the AIMALL program package [24]. To validate

the results obtained from QTAIM analysis, the multi-wave function analysis was performed by Multiwfn software [25]. To explore the reactive sites of the **RT**, the electrostatic potential surfaces were plotted. In addition, molecular docking analysis of **RT** with Retinoid-X receptors was performed by using AutoDock 4.2 software [26].

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Optimized Geometry

The electronic structure of **RT** was optimized at B3LYP and WB97XD functionals with 6-311++G(d,p) basis set combinations, and the structural parameters such as bond lengths, bond angles, and dihedral angles are listed in Table S1 (Supplementary Material). The **RT** molecule consists of an unsaturated C-C linear chain and a cyclohexane ring with three methyl groups substituted in it. A chemically active functional group, CH₂OH, is present at the end of the linear chain, as depicted in Figure 1. Since the crystallographic structure of **RT** is not resolved, the experimental geometrical parameters of Retinoic acid [27] were compared with optimized geometrical parameters of **RT**. The root mean square deviation (RMSD) of available experimental bond angles from the optimized ones is calculated as 0.99624 Å (B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)) and 0.96765 Å (WB97XD/6-311++G(d,p)). The RMSD values obtained for both basis functionals are near to one, indicating that the experimental and theoretical bond parameters agree well. For further calculation of vibrational frequencies and charge transfer analysis, WB97XD is used to incorporate dispersion correction into the system.

The O1-H51 bond distance is predicted to be 0.9633 Å and 0.9588 Å at B3LYP and WB97XD, respectively, with a 6-311++G (d,p) basis set, while the experimental bond distance is 0.840. This discrepancy is due to the low scattering angles of X-rays by the hydrogen atoms during the experiment. The C-C bond lengths of an aromatic C-C chain, such as C₂-C₃, C₂-C₅, C₂-C₈, and C₄-C₆, are observed to be slightly longer than those of a linear chain (C₁₅-C₁₆, C₁₇-C₁₈, and C₂₀-C₂₁). With the help of a quantum topological investigation of electron density, intramolecular hydrogen bonding interactions were identified. The intramolecular bond distances of H₄₉⋯O₁ (2.007 Å), H₅₀⋯O₁ (2.07 Å), and H₄₈⋯O₁ (2.703 Å) were predicted by the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) basis set. The predicted intramolecular lengths are significantly less than the van der Waals forces between the H atom and the O atom, which are less than 3 Å.

Fig.1. Optimized structure of RT using WB97XD/6-311++G(d,p) level of approximation

The quantum theory of atoms in molecule (QTAIM) gives insights into the hydrogen bonding interactions in terms of electron density (ρ_{BCP}) and its Laplacian ($\nabla^2\rho_{\text{BCP}}$) and its associated parameters include Bond Ellipticity (ϵ), kinetic energy density of electron (G_{BCP}), delocalization index (DI), potential energy density of electron (V_{BCP}), Hydrogen bond energy (E_{HB}) at a bond critical point (BCP). Moreover, the nature of intramolecular hydrogen bonding interactions were analyzed using the bond ellipticity (ϵ) and delocalization index (DI). The generated molecular graph paths of **RT** using the AIM 2000 program at WB7XD/B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) basis sets are displayed in Fig.2. Geometrical as well as topological parameters for bond critical point interactions are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Topological parameters obtained from AIM analysis for optimized structures of **RT** at WB97XD/6-311++G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) levels of approximation.

WB97XD/6-311++G(d,p)								
Atoms involved in interactionsBC P and their types (3,-1)	* ρ_{BCP} (a.u)	* $\nabla^2\rho_B$ CP (a.u)	* G_{BCP} (a.u)	* V_{BCP} (a.u)	* H_{BCP}	*DI (a.u)	*E _{HB}	Bond Ellipticity (ϵ) (a.u)
C21-H50...H46	0.0128	0.043	0.0090	-0.0071	0.0019	0.0298	2.228	0.5011
C14-H39...H43	0.0120	0.042	0.0088	-0.0068	0.0019	0.0263	2.138	0.6311
B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p)								
C21-H50...H46	0.0127	0.0430	0.0088	-0.0068	0.0019	0.0300	2.1520	0.4822
C14-H39...H43	0.0119	0.0423	0.0086	-0.0066	0.0019	0.0271	2.0830	0.5922
C8-H29...H34	0.0119	0.0460	0.0095	-0.0073	0.0020	0.0207	2.2800	1.6941

*(ρ :Electron density (a.u.) ; $\nabla^2\rho$: Laplacian of electron density (a.u.); G: Lagrangian kinetic energy (a.u.); V: Potential energy density (a.u.); Bond Ellipticity (ϵ) (a.u.) ; E_{HB}: H-bond energy (kcal/mol)). BCP: Bond critical point;

Fig.2. Topological molecular graph of **RT** generated from the optimized geometries at (a) WB97XD/6-311++G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) levels of approximation

A positive value of $\nabla^2\rho$ obtained for non-bonded atoms confirms the weak noncovalent interaction between the atoms wherein the potential energy density of electron $V(r)$ is lesser than its kinetic energy density $G(r)$. The negative value of $\nabla^2\rho$ at BCP confirms the presence of covalent bonds between the atoms. The electron density (ρ) essentially reflects the nature of the interactions. The value of ρ higher than 0.1 a.u at BCP confirms the existence of strong interactions like electrostatic hydrogen bonding interactions while the value of ρ lesser than 0.1 a.u at BCP signifies the weak van der Waals interactions [28]. In **RT**, the positive value of $\nabla^2\rho$ and total electron density (H) obtained for the interactions C21-H50...H46 and C14-H39...H43 indicates non-covalent interactions. Also, the calculated value of ρ at nonbonded BCPs are less than 0.1 a.u confirms the existence of van der Waals interactions between the non-bonded atoms. As directed by Matta *et al.* [29] the bond ellipticity value ranges between 0.1007 – 0.2885 a.u can be attributed to weak interactions. In the case of **RT**, the higher unusual values of bond ellipticity are due to weaker bond

strength and topological instability. The calculated value of DI for the non-bonded interactions formed via BCPs is also depicted in Table 1. In accordance with Rozas *et al.* [30], the strength of hydrogen bonds observed are found to be weak. The computed electron density values of **RT** at the BCP lie between the range of 0.0128 -0.0118 a.u. which is closer to the values obtained by Popelier and Koch for weak hydrogen bonding [31,32]. The hydrogen bond energies of **RT** at BCPs were calculated as suggested by Espinosa *et al.* [33] The interaction energy of the non-bonded H...H interactions were predicted to be around 2.1 kcal/mol.

4.2 Reduced density gradient analysis (RDG)

The multi-wave function analysis has been implemented to analyze the intramolecular interactions in terms of 2D scatter plot [34] and isosurface density plot using multiwfn software. Initially, the cube files for the real spatial functions $\lambda_2\rho$ (electron density (ρ) multiplied by the sign of the second Hessian eigenvalue (λ_2)) and RDG were generated.

In RDG analyses, the function of $\lambda_2\rho$ ranges from -0.035 to 0.000 a.u. and an isosurface value of 0.5 was fixed. In the RDG plot, the intramolecular interactions were identified using a BGR (blue, green, red) color coding scheme. The BGR scheme is used to indicate H-bond interactions, van der Waals interactions and steric effects, respectively. The 2D scatter plots and the RDG isosurface density of **RT** are given in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. 2D scatter and isosurface density plots illustrating the non-bonded interactions of **RT**

In the 2D scatter plot, the strong hydrogen bonding is signified as blue, wherein $\lambda_2\rho < 0$ (smaller than -0.015 a.u for **RT**). The green color spikes appear in the region where $\lambda_2\rho = 0$ confirms the weak noncovalent interactions. The spikes in the region where $\lambda_2\rho > 0$ (colored in red) indicate the steric repulsion of the aromatic ring. From the RDG isosurface, the green color spikes can be seen between the ranges -0.015 to 0.00 a.u in the middle of the methyl and methylene group surfaces, which replicate the existence of non-covalent interactions. Moreover, the red-green mixed spike in the range between 0.00 and 0.012 a.u confirms the $C-H\cdots\pi$ interactions. The red spike in the center of the trimethylcyclohexane ring reflects an intense steric effect and the red spike appears between 0.013 to 0.020 a.u in the scatter plot confirms the steric repulsion of the aromatic carbons. The presence of small red patches between the hydrogen atoms of the molecule in the isosurface demonstrates higher exchange energy which is due to strong steric repulsion of the aromatic carbons.

4.3 NBO analysis

To validate the substituent and steric effects in **RT** molecule, the hybrid directionality and bond bending investigations of the natural hybrid orbitals (NHO) are employed. Table 2 shows the angle of deviation from the direction of the line connecting the two nuclear centers in the substituents. The ring is distorted because the NHOs of C_7 , C_{11} , C_8 , C_3 and C_2 have deviated from the line of σ (C_7-C_{11}), $\sigma(C_2-C_8)$ and $\sigma(C_2-C_3)$ centers by 2.4° , 1.7° , 1.8° , 1.5° and 2.3° , 1.9° respectively due to the steric effect of the ring. Deviation of O_1 , C_{21} in NHOs from the line of σ (O_1-C_{21}) centers by 1.0° and 3.2° provides a strong charge-transfer path in which the electron-donating oxygen atom is substituted.

Table 2. NHO directionality and “bond bending”

Bond (A-B)	*Deviation at A ($^\circ$)	Deviation at B ($^\circ$)
σ (C_7-C_{11})	2.4	1.7
$\sigma(C_2-C_8)$	1.8	1.5
$\sigma(C_2-C_3)$	2.3	1.9
$\sigma(O_1-C_{21})$	1.0	3.2

* Deviations from the line of nuclear centers

Table 3. Second-order perturbation theory analysis of Fock matrix in NBO basis

DonorNBO's (i)	ED (i) (e)	Acceptor NBO's (j)	ED(j) (e)	*E(2) kcal/mol	*E(j)-E(i) a.u.	*F(i,j) a.u.
$\sigma(\text{O1-C21})$	1.99223	$\sigma^*(\text{C21-H49})$	0.02280	161.72	3.62	0.685
$\sigma(\text{O1-H51})$	1.99036	$\sigma^*(\text{C20-H48})$	0.01677	98.94	3.16	0.5
$\sigma(\text{O1-H51})$	1.99036	$\sigma^*(\text{C21-H49})$	0.02280	216.69	3.48	0.777
$\sigma(\text{O1-H51})$	1.99036	$\sigma^*(\text{C21-H50})$	0.02750	86.01	3.09	0.462
$\sigma(\text{C2-C5})$	1.95560	$\sigma^*(\text{C20-H48})$	0.01677	28.47	2.97	0.261
$\sigma(\text{C2-C5})$	1.95560	$\sigma^*(\text{C21-H49})$	0.02280	50.35	3.29	0.365
$\sigma(\text{C3-H22})$	1.98061	$\sigma^*(\text{C21-H49})$	0.02280	23.65	3.24	0.248
$\sigma(\text{C3-H23})$	1.97846	$\sigma^*(\text{C21-H49})$	0.02280	13.42	3.25	0.186
$\sigma(\text{C5-C7})$	1.97069	$\sigma^*(\text{C20-H48})$	0.01677	14.9	3.15	0.194
$\sigma(\text{C8-H30})$	1.98762	$\sigma^*(\text{C21-H50})$	0.02750	19.68	2.87	0.213
$\pi(\text{C10-C12})$	1.89810	$\pi^*(\text{C13-C15})$	0.15667	18.26	0.46	0.083
$\sigma(\text{C10-H34})$	1.96981	$\sigma^*(\text{C12-H38})$	0.01867	6.47	1.12	0.076
$\pi(\text{C13-C15})$	1.83955	$\pi^*(\text{C16-C17})$	0.13890	19.98	0.45	0.085
$\sigma(\text{C15-H42})$	1.97334	$\sigma^*(\text{C13-C14})$	0.02374	8.22	1.09	0.085
$\pi(\text{C16-C17})$	1.86717	$\pi^*(\text{C13-C15})$	0.15667	19.88	0.46	0.086
$\pi(\text{C16-C17})$	1.86717	$\pi^*(\text{C18-C20})$	0.11776	18.53	0.47	0.083
$\pi(\text{C18-C20})$	1.88454	$\pi^*(\text{C16-C17})$	0.13890	20.01	0.46	0.086
LP(1)O1	1.98076	$\sigma^*(\text{C20-H48})$	0.01677	87.03	3.09	0.463
LP(1)O1	1.98076	$\sigma^*(\text{C21-H49})$	0.02280	63.24	3.41	0.415
LP(1)O1	1.98076	$\sigma^*(\text{C21-H50})$	0.02750	65.96	3.02	0.399
LP(2)O1	1.95744	$\sigma^*(\text{C20-C21})$	0.02268	6.38	0.91	0.068
$\pi^*(\text{C10-C12})$	0.10811	$\pi^*(\text{C5-C7})$	0.10904	10.87	0.03	0.048
$\pi(\text{C5-C7})$	1.90914	$\pi^*(\text{C10-C12})$	0.10811	7.85	0.46	0.054
$\sigma(\text{C8-H28})$	1.98875	$\sigma^*(\text{C20-H48})$	0.01677	32.78	2.91	0.276

*E (2) means energy of hyperconjugative interactions, E (j)-E (i) Energy difference between donor and acceptor i and j NBO orbitals, F (i, j) is the Fock matrix element between i and j NBO orbitals.

The interpretation of hyperconjugative interactions, as well as electron density transfer from filled lone pair electrons, are investigated using NBO analysis. The second-order perturbation energies were used to investigate all feasible interactions between the filled (donor) Lewis-type NBOs (n , σ and π) and empty (acceptor) non-Lewis NBOs (σ^* and π^*) were obtained from. NBO calculations of **RT** were performed using WB97XD/6-311++G (d,p) level the feasible hyperconjugative interactions are listed in Table 3.

From Table 3, it is noted that the interaction between lone pair oxygen atoms of **RT** has an occupancy of ~ 2.0 . The charge transfer species such as $\sigma(\text{O1}) \rightarrow \sigma^*(\text{C20-H48})$, $\sigma(\text{O1}) \rightarrow \sigma^*(\text{C21-H49})$, and $\sigma(\text{O1}) \rightarrow \sigma^*(\text{C21-H50})$, stabilize the system with the energies of about 87.03, 63.24 and 65.96 kcal/mol respectively. The charge transfer interactions between bonding and antibonding orbitals such as $\sigma(\text{O1-C21}) \rightarrow \sigma^*(\text{C21-H49})$, $\sigma(\text{O1-H51}) \rightarrow \sigma^*(\text{C21-H49})$ with $E^{(2)}$ values of 161.72 kcal/mol and 216.69 kcal/mol lead to the maximum stabilization of the **RT** through charge delocalization. The charge delocalization from $\sigma(\text{O1-H51})$ to $\sigma^*(\text{C21-H49})$ clearly displays that the hydroxyl group actively participates in the charge transfer with a stabilization energy of 216.69 kcal/mol.

4.4 Vibrational frequency analysis

In this study, we have examined the spectral and spectroscopic characteristics of **RT** using both experimental and theoretical IR and Raman spectra analysis. **RT** is composed of 51 atoms, which exhibit a total of 147 normal modes of vibration. For each normal mode, we computed the potential energy distribution (PED) and symmetry coordinates of **RT**. The comprehensive vibrational assignments for the fundamental modes of **RT**, along with the corresponding PED values, can be found in Table S2 (Supplementary Material). Additionally, Figures 4 and 5 present the experimental and theoretical FT-IR and FT-Raman plots, respectively.

Fig. 4. Experimental FT-IR and simulated IR spectra of RT

Fig.5. Experimental FT-Raman and simulated Raman spectra of RT

4.4.1 O-H Vibrations

The hydroxyl (O-H) group in **RT** generates three distinct vibrations: stretching, in-plane bending, and out-of-plane bending vibrations. This particular group is highly sensitive to its surroundings, resulting in noticeable shifts in the spectra of hydrogen-bonded assemblies. Typically, OH stretching vibrations manifest in the 3400-3500 cm^{-1} range [35]. In the case of **RT**, we observed a broad peak with its highest intensity at 3430 cm^{-1} in the FT-IR solid-phase spectrum (Experimental), and 3697 cm^{-1} in the gas phase spectrum (Theoretical), representing a deviation of approximately 267 cm^{-1} . This deviation may be attributed to the presence of intermolecular hydrogen bond interactions with neighbouring molecules and basis set deficiency due to the neglect of anharmonic modes. The PED analysis reveals a pure mode that makes a precise 100% contribution.

Generally, the O-H in-plane bending vibration is typically observed within the spectral range of 1150-1250 cm^{-1} [36]. In the case of **RT**, this specific vibration is appeared to be a weak band at 1224 cm^{-1} in both the FT-IR and Raman spectra. The corresponding peaks were predicted to be at 1237 and 1250 cm^{-1} using DFT calculations. On the other hand, the O-H out-of-plane bending vibration is typically found within the spectral range of 517-710 cm^{-1} [37]. In the FT-IR and FT-Raman spectra of **RT**, the bands corresponding to O-H out-of-plane bending modes were observed at 694 cm^{-1} and 703 cm^{-1} , respectively, while the theoretically computed wavenumber at 676 cm^{-1} closely matches with this band.

4.4.2 C-O Vibrations

The stretching vibrations associated with benzoic acids and their derivatives are typically found within the spectral range of 1300-1000 cm^{-1} . In a study conducted by Aayisha et al. [38], C-O stretching modes were identified at 1359, 1341, 1035, 990, and 915 cm^{-1} in the FT-IR spectrum, as well as 1360 and 930 cm^{-1} in the FT-Raman spectrum. Nataraj et al. [39] reported C-O stretching vibration values of 1216, 1183, and 1022 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum and 1257 and 1181 cm^{-1} in the Raman spectrum. Karthick et al. [40] assigned C-O vibrational modes at 1046 cm^{-1} in the FT-IR and 1050 cm^{-1} in the FT-Raman spectrum. In the current investigation, we observed C-O stretching mode of **RT** in the FT-Raman bands at 1147 cm^{-1} and IR bands at 1047 cm^{-1} .

4.4.3 C-C Vibrations

The C-C stretching modes typically produce peaks within the spectral range from 1650 to 1200 cm^{-1} [41]. In **RT** molecule, the peaks identified in the FT-IR spectrum at 1461 cm^{-1} and 1437 cm^{-1} in the FT-Raman spectrum were attributed to the vibrations of the C-C ring. The observed peaks in the FT-IR and FT-Raman are in good agreement with the computed values of 1442 and 1433 cm^{-1} obtained through the WB97XD/6-311++G(d,p) method. Additionally, the C-C in-plane bending modes are identified at 584 and 635 cm^{-1} in the FT-Raman spectrum and calculated harmonic wavenumber of 679 cm^{-1} is assigned to this mode. The corresponding out-of-plane bending modes are identified at 569 and 703 cm^{-1} in FT-IR and FT-Raman spectra, respectively. These observed frequencies coincide with the values presented in Table S2 (Supplementary Material).

4.4.4 Methoxy group vibrations

In the present investigation on **RT**, the CH_3 groups act as a primary role as they are typically recognized as electron-donating substituents within the aromatic ring system. These CH_3 groups are associated with nine fundamental vibrational modes, include symmetric stretching ($\nu_{\text{SS}} \text{CH}_3$) and antisymmetric stretching ($\nu_{\text{AS}} \text{CH}_3$), symmetric (βCH_3) and antisymmetric (δCH_3) deformation, in-plane stretching modes (in-plane hydrogen stretching), as well as in-plane rocking ($\rho_{\text{in}} \text{CH}_3$), out-of-plane rocking ($\rho_{\text{out}} \text{CH}_3$), and twisting (τCH_3) bending modes. Generally, one can expect CH_3 asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations within the range of 2962 cm^{-1} to 2872 cm^{-1} [42]. In the infrared (IR) spectrum, we observed strong absorptions at 2863 cm^{-1} , due to the asymmetric CH_3 stretching modes, while in the Raman spectrum, the symmetric stretching is identified at 2955 cm^{-1} .

The changes in the CH_3 stretching mode are influenced by electronic effects due to hyperconjugation between the methyl group and the aromatic ring system. This interaction leads to alterations in polarizability and dipole moment, arising from electron delocalization [43]. Symmetric and asymmetric methyl deformation modes typically appear around 1460 cm^{-1} and 1375 cm^{-1} . The IR band at 1461 cm^{-1} is attributed to CH_3 symmetric deformation mode. Umbrella modes are typically observed around $1375 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and based on existing literature, we anticipate the IR band at 1371 cm^{-1} and the Raman band at 1370 cm^{-1} correspond to the umbrella mode. The position of the umbrella mode is generally less sensitive to changes compared to C-H stretching. The CH_3 rocking mode vibration is anticipated to fall within the 1070-900 cm^{-1} range [44], with the IR band at 957 cm^{-1} and the Raman band at 1040 cm^{-1} being assigned to the CH_3 rocking mode of **RT**.

4.4.5 Methylene group vibrations

As reported by Kavitha et al., the asymmetric stretching vibration of CH₂ groups typically appears within the spectral range of 3000-2900 cm⁻¹, while the symmetric CH₂ stretching vibration is commonly found in the range of 2900-2800 cm⁻¹ [45]. A weak band at 2927 cm⁻¹ (FT-IR) is attributed to CH₂ asymmetric stretching vibrations. Conversely, CH₂ symmetric vibrations appeared as a strong intensity band at 3016 cm⁻¹ in the Raman spectrum. Scissoring vibrations of CH₂ groups are typically observed within the 1500-800 cm⁻¹ range, and in our study, we have detected these vibrations at 871 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum and 924 cm⁻¹ in the Raman spectrum. These values closely align with the scaled values of 871 and 926 cm⁻¹. CH₂ wagging and rocking vibrations are commonly found within the 1400-900 cm⁻¹ range. We have observed CH₂ wagging vibrations at 957 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum and 974 cm⁻¹ in the Raman spectrum. Additionally, we have detected mixed twisting with the rocking band at 859 and 1040 cm⁻¹ in the Raman spectrum, and these values correlate with scaled values of 861 and 1039 cm⁻¹.

4.5 Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MEP) surfaces

The molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) is a valuable tool for investigating the chemical reactivity of molecular systems and studying hydrogen bonding. To study the reactive sites of **RT**, the MEP calculation was performed using the WB97XD functional and the 6-311++G(d,p) basis set. On the MEP surface, atomic sites are color-coded to represent their electrostatic potential. Blue indicates regions with the strongest repulsion, which signifies susceptibility to nucleophilic attacks. Conversely, red indicates regions of the strongest attraction, making them prone to electrophilic attacks. Green represents areas with a neutral potential, suitable for radical attacks. The electrostatic potential of atoms follows the order: red < orange < yellow < green < blue. A visual representation of the MEP surface contour map of the **RT** molecule is given in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Total density mapped with molecular electrostatic potential surface of Retinol

The MEP analysis helps to understand the charge distributions within the molecule. Specifically, atom O1 exhibits the highest electronegative charges, while atoms H50 and C21 carry significant positive charges. In addition, regions marked in green on the MEP surface correspond to potentials between the extremes represented by blue (indicating strong repulsion or nucleophilic susceptibility) and red (indicating strong attraction or electrophilic susceptibility). Electrostatic charges calculated using the WB97XD and B3LYP methods can be found in Table S3 of the Supplementary Material. For instance, the fitting point charges for atom O1 are determined as -0.76595 a.u. and -0.80555 a.u. using the WB97XD and B3LYP methods, respectively. In the case of our molecule, RT, hydrogen atoms and a methyl group linked to the ring system exhibit relatively lower positive charges. Notably, hydrogen atom H51 has a charge of approximately 0.4404 e and is within a predominantly nucleophilic region. Conversely, atom C21 bears a highly positive charge of around 0.673 e, yet the MEP map over C21 appears yellow in color. This apparent discrepancy arises because C21 is surrounded by regions with a strong electrophilic character. These calculated results indicate that positive potential sites are primarily associated with hydrogen atoms, while negative potential sites are predominantly located on electronegative oxygen atoms.

4.8 Frontier Molecular Orbitals

The frontier molecular orbitals are pivotal in shaping a molecule's reactivity and chemical stability. Among these, the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) hold particular significance. The HOMO signifies the molecule's capacity to donate an electron, while the LUMO indicates its ability to accept an electron. Additionally, the energy of the HOMO correlates directly with the ionization potential ($I = -E_{\text{HOMO}}$), and the LUMO energy is directly related to the electron affinity ($A = -E_{\text{LUMO}}$). In accordance with molecular orbital theory, the interaction between HOMO and LUMO orbitals gives rise to π - π^* type state transitions [46]. In our present study, we calculated the energies of the frontier molecular orbitals, including HOMO, HOMO-1, HOMO-2, LUMO, LUMO+1, and LUMO+2, using the WB97XD/6-311++G(d,p) method. The positive and negative regions of these frontier molecular orbitals are visually represented in Figure 7. According to the WB97XD level of theory, we determined the energy band gap ΔE , which represents the energy difference between HOMO and LUMO orbital values, to be 7.1361 eV for **RT** molecule. A substantial HOMO-LUMO energy gap suggests high stability, indicating lower charge transfer in complexes. The HOMO is primarily situated above the bonding π orbitals, which extend across all carbon atoms, contributing to the molecule's structural integrity. Non-bonding orbital lobes are localized on the oxygen atom's surface within the HOMO. In contrast, the LUMO is distributed across the entire molecule, except for the ring and methyl groups. Notably, all the HOMO surfaces (HOMO, HOMO-1, HOMO-2) are predominantly concentrated on the ring and hydroxyl substitutions, while all the LUMO surfaces exhibit orbital overlap with the methane groups. In addition to HOMO, LUMO energies, the other reactive descriptors (Table 4) of **RT** molecule are calculated by using the relations as suggested in the literature [47].

Fig. 7. Electron density surface map of molecular orbitals of the retinol

Table 4. Calculated energy values of RT by WB97XD /6-311++G(d, p)

Parameters (eV)	Values
E_{HOMO}	-7.1217
E_{LUMO}	0.0144
Energy band gap	7.1361
Ionization potential	7.1217
Electron affinity	-0.0144
Chemical hardness	3.5680
Chemical Softness	0.1401
Electronegativity	3.5536
Chemical potential	-3.5536
Electrophilicity index	1.7696
Maximum Charge transfer index	0.9959

4.9 Drug Likeness

In drug discovery, the structural characteristics of ligands and drug-likeness studies hold paramount importance. The drug-likeness of a given ligand can be evaluated using various criteria, including Lipinski's rule, MDDR-like rules, Ghose filter, Veber's rule, CMC-50 rule, BBB rule, and QED [48]. Critical ADME parameters, including Hydrogen bond acceptors (HBA), Hydrogen bond donors (HBD), rotatable bonds, Molar refractivity (MR), gastrointestinal (GI) absorption, Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB) penetration, Topological Polar Surface Area (TPSA), log K_p (skin permeability), and bioavailability score, have been computed for the compound under investigation and are presented in Table 5.

Lipinski's rule of five, is a common practice in understanding drug molecules [48, 49]. As indicated in Table 5, **RT** does not meet one of Lipinski's rules of five. Specifically, **RT** has one hydrogen bond donor and acceptor, fulfilling Lipinski's rule. Moreover, **RT** exhibits high GI absorption and the capability to penetrate the blood-brain barrier. The predicted skin permeability (log K_p) for **RT** is approximately -4.01 cm/s. However, the calculated log P value is 6.09, which violates one of Lipinski's rules of five. The molar refractivity of **RT** is determined to be 94.67, well

within the appropriate range [50]. The drug-likeness score for **RT** is estimated at 0.73, signifying its potential as a promising drug candidate.

Table. 5. Drug likeness parameters of Retinol molecule.

Descriptor	Values
Hydrogen Bond Donor (HBD)	1
Hydrogen Bond Acceptor (HBA)	1
Molecular weight	286.45 g/mol
TPSA [\AA^2]	20.23 [\AA^2]
Molar refractivity (MR)	94.67
Number of heavy atoms	21
MLogP	6.09 (>5)
Number of rotatable bonds	5
GI absorption	High
Log K_p	-4.01 cm/s
BBB permanent	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	Yes
Lipinski violations	Yes (1)
Bioavailability Score	0.55

4.7 Molecular Docking

Molecular docking analysis is used to identify optimal binding sites for ligand molecules within the vicinity of retinoid binding receptors. Specifically, we conducted a molecular docking study to assess various biological activities of **RT** against human binding proteins, targeting receptors including 5NTY (Plasma RT-binding protein), 7B88 (Retinoid X receptor alpha), 5OGB (Retinoid X receptor beta), and 2GL8 (Retinoid X receptor gamma). These proteins were selected based on their predicted binding affinity, as determined using the Swiss target prediction web interface [51,52]. We obtained the PDB structures of these target proteins from the RCSB Protein Data Bank and conducted docking analysis using Auto Dock Tools (ADT). Hydrogen bond interactions between the ligand and the

proteins were visualized using Pymol Software. Before docking analysis, the ligand underwent energy minimization and optimization at the WB97XD/6-311++g(d,p) level of theory. Figure 8 shows hydrogen bonds were identified between oxygen and hydrogen atoms from the protein and the ligand. **RT** was docked into the binding pocket of 5NTY, forming four hydrogen bonds with ARG 121, GLN 98, and GLY 34, resulting in a favorable binding energy of approximately -9.29 kcal/mol. Details of these interactions are presented in Table 6. In all cases, the hydrogen bond distances fell within the 1.5 to 3.6 Å range. The binding energies of **RT** with the selected proteins: 5NTY, 7B88, 5OGB, and 2GL8 were estimated as -9.29 kcal/mol, -7.79 kcal/mol, -7.36 kcal/mol, and -7.21 kcal/mol, respectively, as listed in Table 6. Notably, all bonded residues in the four proteins were found within the allowed region of the Ramachandran plot. Our docking results reveal that the electronegative nitrogen atom is the primary site of hydrogen bond formation with the selected target proteins, confirming the bioactivity of **RT** molecule.

Table 6. Molecular docking result of Retinol with different target proteins.

Protein (PDB ID)	Bonded residues	Bond distance (Å)	Inhibition constant	Binding energy (kcal/mol)	Ligand efficiency	Intermolecular energy (kcal/mol)	Reference RMSD
3U2C	TRP 20	2.3	249.19 (nM)	-9.01	-0.43	-10.8	19.13
	THR 19	1.8					
	ASP 43	3.5					
	ASP 43	3.0					
2KT4	GLY 43	3.1	6.51 (µM)	-7.08	-0.34	-8.87	6.53
	GLU 44	3.3					
	LYS 68	2.6					
6DUM	ASP 392	3.0	3.14 (µM)	-7.51	-0.36	-9.3	40.84
	ARG 308	2.0					
5W9D	ASN 519	2.9	27.15 (µM)	-6.23	-0.3	-8.02	37.34
	HIS 516	2.4					

Fig. 8. Molecular docking of RT against macromolecular targets a)3U2C b)2RCT c) 2RCQ d) 6GXK

4.8 Conclusion

In the present work, a comprehensive study on the structural, vibrational, electronic, topology analysis of **RT** was carried out with the aid of quantum chemical calculations. From the NBO analysis, anti-bonding and lone pairs orbital species which are responsible for the stabilization of molecule were predicted by WB97XD/6-311++G (d,p). The spectral assignments of experimental IR and Raman bands was done using PED analysis. Electrostatic point charges on atoms exhibited that the atom O₁ belongs to the most electrophilic region and the atom H₅₀,C₂₁ belongs to the most nucleophilic region. HOMO–LUMO energy gap confirmed that the charge transfer occurs within the **RT** molecule. Non-covalent interactions approach distinguishes the strong attraction, weak attractive interactions, and steric repulsion that occurred in the **RT**. Molecular docking of **RT** is carried out with the target proteins substantiate that **RT** can be a good bio-active agent. However, the activity of **RT** against the target proteins need to be confirmed through in-vitro and in-vivo experiments.

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